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Synergistic Effects of Ethanolic Extract of *Ocimum Sanctum* and Omega 3 Fatty Acid on Mice Infected With *Plasmodium Berghei*

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Abstract: This study was carried out to investigate the synergistic effect of ethanolic extract of *Ocimum sanctum* and Omega 3 fatty acids on mice infected with *P. berghei*. The parameters analyzed include a qualitative phytochemical screening of *Ocimum sanctum*, toxicity study of LD₅₀ of *O. sanctum*, level of parasitaemia rate after treatment, Biochemical indices and enzymes assays. All parameters were analyzed using the standard method of analysis. The qualitative phytochemical screening of *O. sanctum* shows high present of volatile oils, and moderately presence of saponins, steroids, cardiac glycoside, and alkaloids, with low presence of flavonoids, Tannins and Antraquinone were absent. Acute toxicity of LD₅₀ of *Ocimum santum* was established at 1,936.49mg/kg. Group F (standard control) and a group of Mice that administered with 300mg/kg + 0.2 cod-liver oils had the highest significant ($P < 0.05$) inhibition rate of parasitaemia ($P < 0.05$) while Positive control group (infected and untreated) had lowest significant ($P < 0.05$) inhibition rate. The synergy of *Ocimum sanctum* and cod-liver oils shows significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in Biochemical indices while group F (standard control) and group A (infected untreated) shows significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in Biochemical indices. The combination of *Ocimum sanctum* and cod-liver shows significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in enzymes assays at different concentration while infected untreated group shows a significant increase in enzymes assay. The study indicates that the combination of *Ocimum sanctum* and Omega 3 fatty acids at different concentration show anti-malarial effects. Damage done to the liver is minimal as indicated in the enzymes assay. Thus the combination of *Ocimum sanctum* and Omega 3 fatty acids can be used as anti-malarial

Keywords: *Ocimum santum*, Omega 3 fatty acid, *Plasmodium berghei*, Enzyme assay, Biochemical indices, Phytochemical

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a parasitic protozoan disease caused by genus *Plasmodium*. Malaria parasite belongs to sub-kingdom protozoa, phylum *Apicomplexa*, classes *Haematozoa*, order *Haemosporida*, family *Plasmodiidae*, genus *Plasmodium*. There are about 156 species of *Plasmodium*, but five are known to causes diseases of human. The five species are *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium ovale malariae*, *Plasmodium knowlesi* (WHO, 2016). The first two are the most common, *Plasmodium falciparum* is most dangerous of these species, because the infection can kill rapidly (within several days) whereas other species cause illness but not death (WHO, 2016). *Plasmodium Berghei* is a Laboratory model parasite that used to study human malaria for the development of new antimalarial drugs (Robert *et al.*, 2002).

The disease primarily affects poor populations in tropical and subtropical areas, where the temperature and rainfall are suitable for the development of vectors and parasites (Greenwood *et al.*, 2008). Snow *et al.*, (2005) reported that more than 40% of the world population is at risk of the disease. World Health Organisation in 2017 estimated that 3.2 billion are at high risk of transmission (≥ 1 case per 1000 population), half of which live in the African regions; 80% of such cases were said to be concentrated in 13 countries, and over half in Nigeria, Congo, Ethiopia, Tanzania and Kenya (WHO, 2008). In 2008, Nigeria accounted for a quarter of all malaria cases in Africa (WHO, 2008). In the southern part of the country, transmission occurs all year round while in the north it is more seasonal. Malaria is the most common disease in Nigeria; according to the World Health Organization (2008) half of the population will have had one or more malaria attacks annually (WHO, 2008).

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Antimalarial drug resistance has been defined as the ability of a parasite strain to survive and/or multiply despite the administration and absorption of a drug given in doses equal to or higher than those usually recommended but within a tolerance of the subject (WHO, 2007). Most resistance strains of *Plasmodium* species have developed due to drugs suppression by asexual stage of parasite merozoites and trophozoite, inadequate drug doses mainly as a result of unregulated drug distribution and prescription, lack of adequate drugs, Poor quality of drug, incorrect taking of drugs by patient, (When insufficient drug is taken to kill the malaria parasites, the mutants survive and multiply) (Arora *et al.*, 2014).

This, in addition to the increased number of drug-resistant parasites, makes the development of novel anti-malarial urgent. The high cost of malaria treatment has left the poor masses of Nigeria heavily reliant on traditional practitioners and medicinal plants for the treatment of this disease (Adebayo and Krettli, 2010).

Malaria is a major public health and socioeconomic problem in sub-Saharan Africa including Nigeria. Every year about one million deaths results as a direct consequence of infection with *Plasmodium* parasites (WHO, 2007). Each year, there are approximately 3.2 billion cases of Malaria (WHO, 2017), killing nearly one million people, the majority of whom are children in sub-Saharan Africa. Recent research shows that there are about billion cases of malaria killing million people yearly (WHO, 2015). One in five childhood deaths are caused by malaria, and for every 30 seconds, someone dies of malaria (Snow *et al.*, 2005). The disease accounts for 25% of infant mortality and 30% childhood mortality in Nigeria (Ayodele *et al.*, 2007). It is a significant cause of abortion, still-birth, low birth weight and death of low-immune pregnant women (Bunza *et al.*, 2010).

It is a major hindrance to economic development in African countries due to poor productivity, and it costs African more than 12 billion dollar in lost GDP every year (Oyewole *et al.*, 2008). Control of malaria is complex because of the appearance of drugs resistance strains. Majority of these available drugs have been rendering useless due to the rapid spread of anti-malaria resistance by *Plasmodium* parasites (Senior, 2005). The high cost of anti-malaria drugs developed to a various degree in several countries with the exception of Artemisin derivative, which is very expensive and their supply is not meeting demand (Senior, 2005).

Malaria parasites developed resistant to synthetic drugs, but do not develop resistant against plants extracts due to its high organic component and phytochemical, biodegradable properties. The herbal plants are cheap and readily available and can be found in large quantity in Nigeria. Plants form the main ingredients in traditional medicine and have been the source of inspiration for several major pharmaceutical drugs industries (WHO, 2002). Omega 3 fatty acids and *O. sanctum* have been reported to have antimalarial and ameliorating effects (Schumann, 2011). It is against this background that this study was carried out to investigate the synergistic effects of Omega 3 fatty acid and *Ocimum sanctum* leave extracts against *Plasmodium berghei*.

The aim of the study is to assess the synergic effect of Omega 3 fatty acids and *Ocimum sanctum* on mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*. The specific objectives are:

1.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Identification of Plants

Ocimum sanctum leaves collected from the University of Science and Technology Aliero. The leave was collected on 3rd July 2017. It was identified and authenticated Dr. Dramendra Singh at herbarium section of Biological Sciences, Botany Units, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, with voucher number 101.

Plant Preparation and Extraction

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Ocimum sanctum leaves were washed with distilled water and dried under shade at room temperature for two weeks. Using clean mortar and pestle, dried leaves were ground to a fine powder. Ethanolic extract of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves was prepared by soaking 200g of ground *Ocimum sanctum* leaves in 2 Litre of ethanol in a conical flask for 48 hours. The resulting mixture was filtered using filter paper; the filtrate was further concentrated in a water bath at 45°C to obtain a jelly-like substance; the extract was stored until when needed. About 5g was weighed and dissolved in 100 ml normal saline to serve as stock solution; the extract was administered at different concentrations accordingly to mice (Kolapo, *et al.*, 2009).

Acquisition of Experimental Animals.

Fifty mice of weight range 19-30g were obtained from Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto Zoological garden.

Acquisition of parasite stock, and mode of infection

Plasmodium berghei (NK-65) strain was obtained from Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Biochemistry laboratory. Blood was taken from donor albino mice previously infected with *Plasmodium berghei* (NK-65) strain, in which the parasitaemia is high and rising (usually 30% or more red cells infected). The number of parasites per 500 red cells was estimated. From the donor mice, 1ml of blood was taken and diluted with 5ml of phosphate buffered, such that 0.1 ml contained standard inoculum of 1×10^7 infected red cells parasites. From the pool of acclimatized mice, thirty mice were randomly selected and were inoculated intraperitoneally from the same source to avoid variability in parasitaemia (Banyal *et al.*, 1991).

Qualitative Phytochemical Screening

The extract was evaluated for the presence of saponin, tannin, flavonoids, alkaloid, anthraquinones, volatile oil, steroid, cardiac glycoside. The analysis was done according to the method described and reviewed by Prashant *et al.*, (2011)

Phytochemical of Saponin Test

Frothing test: about 5ml of the ethanolic extract of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves was poured into a test tube; it was vigorously shaken for 3 minutes. Frothing observed in the extract indicated the presence of saponin.

Tannins Test

To 1ml of freshly prepared 10% potassium hydroxide (KOH) 1ml of the extract was added. A dirty white precipitate observed in extract indicated the presence of tannins.

Flavonoid Test

One millilitre of 10% NaOH was added to 3ml of extract. A yellow coloration observed indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Free Anthraquinones Test

To 5ml of the extract, 10ml of benzene was added shaken, and the presence of pink, red or violet colour in ammoniacal (lower) phase indicated the presence of free anthraquinones.

Alkaloids Test

To 1ml of 1% Hydrochloric acid, added to ethanolic extract in a test tube was added. The mixture was heated for 20 minutes, cooled and filtered, the filtrate was treated with few drops of Wagner's reagent and a second 1ml

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portion was treated with Mayer's reagent. Reddish brown precipitate for Wagner's and creamy for Mayer's reagent indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Volatile Oils Test

To 1ml of extract, dilute Hydrochloric acid was mixed. A white precipitate form indicated the presence of volatile oil.

Steroid Test

One milliliter of the extract was dissolved into 2ml of chloroform and 2ml of sulphuric acid carefully added to form a lower layer. A reddish brown colour at the interface indicated the presence of steroid.

Cardiac Glycoside

To 2ml of the extract, 2ml of acetic acid containing traces of FeCl_3 was added to 2ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 was carefully poured down, the wall of the tube to form a lower layer. A reddish-brown ring at the interface while the upper layer becomes green to blue layer indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Determination of Toxicity Test

Ocimum sanctum leaves were tested for acute toxicity in mice using Lorke's method.

Calculation of LD_{50} was done using the formula, $\text{LD}_{50} = \sqrt{x \times y}$

Where: x = minimum mortality dose,

y = maximum survival dose

From the pool of acclimatized rats, twenty mice were picked randomly.

The group base on dose was as follows: group 1 received 500mg, group 2 received 1500mg, group 3 received 2500mg, Group 4 received 3500mg, and the group was 5 fed with food and water. The mice were observed for abnormalities for a duration of 48 hours. The Mice were constantly monitored and changes observed, such as movement, respiratory problem, response to sound, hair removal, loss of appetite, weakness and finally dead were recorded (Lorke, 1983).

1.3 Experimental Designs

Synergistic effects of *Ocimum sanctum* leave, and Omega 3 fatty acid against *P. beighei* was carried out using Peter's 4 day -Test (Peter, 1970). Thirty infected mice were used, and mice were divided into six groups, five mice per group. Group 1 (positive control, infected untreated) received water and food, group 2 received (100mg/kg + 0.2 Omega 3 fatty acids), group 3 received (200mg/kg + 0.2 Omega 3 fatty acids), group 4 received (300mg/kg + Omega 3 fatty acids) group 5 received (0.2 Omega 3 fatty acids), group 6 received (Artemether/lumefantrine) standard control. All group was treated for 4 days; all experimental animal were given food and water of equal proportion.

Blood sampling collection

Blood from the tail of all experimental animals was collected for the preparation of blood films.

Preparation of the blood Films

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Blood from a clean grease, free glass slide, drop of blood was placed, and thin film was made by holding the slide and spreader at angle of 45° the spreader was pushed along the slide with a smooth movement, this allows the blood to run along the edge of spreader until the whole blood was smeared, the smear was slightly thick at the origin than at the tail end. To make a thick film another drop of blood was spread with the corner of the clean slide to an even thickness on the slide and was left to air dry (WHO, 2008).

Fixing and Staining

After the blood smears are dried, each thin film was fixed with 100% methanol and left to air dry. These were placed back to back in a staining trough with all thick film at one end of the trough, 3% solution of giemsa stain was poured gently in to the trough until the slides were totally covered. The slides were left for 30 minutes after which clean water was slowly pouring from a beaker in to trough to float off the iridescent "scum" on the surface of the stain. The staining solution in the trough was gently poured off. The slides were removed after the other using a forceps, and they were dipped in ordinary water for few seconds and placed in drying rack to air dry (WHO, 2008).

Microscopic Examination

Examination of the slide was carried out by viewing the blood film through the low powered objective to ensure that the distribution of cells was satisfactory and to observe an area where the cells were free from distortion. Having found a suitable area, a detailed examination of the morphology was undertaken. Approximately 100 fields of thin films were examined to determine the presence of *Plasmodium berghei* under x100 oil immersion objective before concluding whether the slide is negative or positive. Positive thin films were examined for parasite under x100 oil immersion. Counting of the parasites was carried out under thin film (WHO, 2008).

The densities of parasites were calculated by the method described by Palmer and Sam, (1999). The numbers of parasites per microliter of blood in a thick film were counted in relation to a standard number of leukocytes (8000).

$$\frac{\text{Number of Parasites}}{200 \text{ (leukocytes)}} \times 8000$$

Or as a percentage of total erythrocytes in thin film

$$\frac{\text{Number of parasitized cell found}}{\text{Number of total erythrocytes scanned}}$$

RESULTS

Qualitative Photochemical Analysis of *Ocimum sanctum* leaf extract

Table 1 shows the qualitative photochemical analysis of *Ocimum sanctum*. The result reveals the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoid, Steroids Volatile Oils, Cardiac Glycosides, free Antraquinone, and Tannin were absent. The result showed highly presents of volatiles oil, moderately present of steroids, Alkaloids Saponin cardiac Glycoside, Low Present of Flavonoids and absent of free Anthraquinone, Tannin. The result of the qualitative photochemical analysis showed high volatiles oil while showed the lowest flavonoids.

4.2. Acute Toxicity Study of *Ocimum sanctum* leaf extract

Table 2 and 3 show the acute toxicity study. Mice administered with 500mg/kg showed no sign of toxicity such as difficulties in respiration, movement, food intake and death. The Mice administered with 2,500mg/kg and 3,500mg/kg showed signs of toxicity which include difficulties in movement, respiration, food intake and death of 3 and 4 mice respectively. The LD₅₀ was established at 1,936.49 as safety dose.

Percentage of Parasitaemia in Experimental miles

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The synergistic effect of Omega 3 fatty acid and *Ocimum sanctum* on *P.beigheiare* presented in Table 4. There was a high increase of Parasitemia level among untreated infected mice while both standard control and extracts treated group recorded low of Parasitaemia. Group F Standard control (ACT) showed the lowest Parasitaemia with 2.04 ± 1.4 Parasitaemia level. Cod liver Oil and *Ocimum sanctum* extract showed dose-dependent, 300mg/kg + 0.2 Cod Liver Oil had 2.63 ± 2.04 Parasitaemia, 200mg/kg + 0.2 Cod Liver Oil had 4.82 ± 4.5 parasitaemia, while 100mg/kg+ 0.2 Cod Liver Oil had 5.76 ± 5.1 . Cod Liver Oil (0.2) had 19.9 ± 7.3 , while positive control the untreated infected mice showed the highest parasitaemia with 58.72 ± 12.7 Parasitaemia level. The statistical analysis of variance showed no significant difference in mean value of group F Standard control (ACT) with 2.04 ± 1.4 when compared with group D (300mg/kg + 0.2 Cod liver oil) with 2.63 ± 2.04 mean value while the statistical analysis showed a significant difference in mean value of group A. infected and untreated which had the highest value when compared with (ACT) which showed the lowest mean value.

TABLE 1: Quantitative phytochemical Screening of *Ocimum sanctum* Leaf Extract.

Composition	Result
Alkaloids	++
Saponin	++
Tannin	-
Steroids	++
Flavonoid	+
Free Antraquinone	-
Volatile oils	+++
Cardiac Glycoside	++

Higher Present +++, Moderately Present ++, Low +, Absent -

Table 2: Acute toxicity study of experimental mice.

Doses	Group A	GroupB	Group C	Group D	Group E
Doses(g/kg)	500mg/kg	1,500mg/kg	2,500mg/kg	3,500mg/Kg	Control
Initial weight	27.5	19.5	21.6	30.9	25.6
Final weight	27.6	19.8	21.8	31.8	25.8
Mean body weight	27.33	19.38	21.43	31.30	25.30
No of mortality	-	-	3	4	-
% of mortality	-	-	60%	80%	-

Table 3: Behavioural changes and death/day

Group	Doses(mg/kg)	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Death/day
A	500	No sign of toxicity	No sign of toxicity	No sign of toxicity	No death
B	1500	No sign of toxicity	No sign of toxicity	No sign of toxicity.	No death
C	2500	instant death of 1 mice, the remaining showed behaviorally changes.	Death of two mice Was observed.	No Death was Observed.	2 death was recorded.
D	3500	instant death of two mice observed	-	death of two was was recorded.	3 death recorded
E	Control 0.3ml Normal saline	Normal activity	Normal activity	Normal activity	Normal activity

Table 4: Percentage of Parasitaemia per Group

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Group	Doses	Percentage of Parasitaemia
A	Positive control	58.72 ± 12.7
B	100mg/kg + 0.2 Cod Liver Oil	5.76 ± 5.1
C	200mg/kg Cod liver Oil	4.82 ± 4.5
D	300mg/kg + 0.2 Cod Liver Oil	2.63 ± 2.04
E	0.2 Cod liver Oil	19.9 ± 7.3
F	Standard Control (ACT)	2.04 ± 1.4

Group	Doses (mg/kg)	ALP(iu/l)	AST(iu/l)	ALT(iu/l)
A	Untreated Infected	224.74 ± 18.45	2.34.33 ± 6.58	92.44 ± 10.76
B	100mg/kg +0.2ul codliver oil	123.41 ± 33.33	35.52 ± 3.56	54.15 ± 3.45
C	200mg/kg + 0.2ul codliver oil	135.42 ± 12.43	43.21 ± 4.89	59.60 ± 7.67
D	300mg/kg + 0.2ul Codliver oil	149.43 ± 24.01	55.35 ± 7.21	58.07 ± 5.66
E	Codliver oil 0.2ul	132.40 ± 14.16	58.22 ± 4.56	61.24 ± 13.20
F	Standard control (ACT)	187.330 ± 21.23	90.18 ± 5.55	66.64 ± 14.48

Data are presented as mean ±SD (P ≤ 0.05)

Table 5: Biochemical indices of Experimental Mice.

Groups	Doses(mg/kg)	Total protein (g/dl)	Total Albumin (g/dl)	Total Biluribin (mg/dl)	Direct Biluribin (mg/dl)
A	Untreated infected Positive control	3.42 ± 1.02	1.56 ± 0.67	1.99 ± 0.15	0.85 ± 0.04
B	100mg/ + 0.2 Cod Liver Oil	4.36 ± 1.11	1.05 ± 0.24	2.22 ± 0.12	0.67 ± 0.08
C	200mg/kg + 0.2ul Cod liver oil	5.23 ± 0.25	1.01 ± 0.11	1.48 ± 0.13	0.82 ± 0.19
D	300mg/kg 0.2ul Cod liver oil	5.06 ± 0.25	1.52 ± 0.63	1.81 ± 0.29	1.55 ± 0.24
E	Cod liver oil 0.2ul	4.80 ± 0.32	1.99 ± 0.54	1.35 ± 0.21	1.49 ± 0.43
F	Standard control (ACT) 0.2ul	3.11 ± 0.48	0.98 ± 0.46	1.79 ± 0.28	1.07 ± 0.28

Data are presented as mean ± SD (P ≤ 0.05)

TABLE 6: Liver Enzymes assay of experimental Mice.

Data are presented as mean ± SD, P ≤ 0.05

ALP= Alkaline Phosphatase, AST= Aspartate Amino Transferase, ALT=Alanine Amino transferase.

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Figure 1: Number of doses and Death/Group

Figure 2: Percentage of Inhibition/Group.

DISCUSSION

The study reveals that Synergistic extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* and omega3 fatty acids possess anti-malarial effect against *Plasmodiumbeighei* infection in mice as evidenced by the percentage of parasitaemia obtained in the study. It was observed that the anti-malarial activities of synergistic extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* and omega3 fatty acid are dose dependent at different concentration. The anti-malarial, anti-inflammatory, immunodulatory, hepato-protective and analgesic activities demonstrated by the synergistic extract of *Ocimum sanctum* and Omega 3 fatty acids could be attributed to their alkaloids, saponons, steroids, volatiles oils cardiac glycosides, flavonoids constituent as observed in this study and as previously reported by Khan and Bhatia, (2003), Chiag *et al.*, (2005), Matur (2009), Ambekar *et al.*, (2016). More over theconstitutes can serve as immune modulators, antioxidants, and inhibitors of haema-polymerisation as reported by byAherne *et al.*,(2007). Particularly saponns and polyphenol have been associated with anti-anemic activities as reported by

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Yakubu *et al.*, (2005). *Ocimum sanctum* has essential oils eugenol and is the main constituents that could be responsible for its anti-malarial, larvicidal/repellent properties as reported by Singhet *et al.*, (2010). Saponin serves as anti-biotic for the body to fight infection and microbial invasion and to increase intestinal permeability (Gbadomosi *et al.*, 2011).

The Acute toxicity test of *Ocimum sanctum* was established at LD₅₀, 1,936.45mg/kg as safety dose. This LD50 result is in agreement with the findings of Ezeonwumelu *et al.*, (2006). The total protein, albumin, bilirubin, direct bilirubin, showed significant increase (p<0.05) in treated group, this may be associated with the effect of active principle saponins and flavonoids, volatiles oils, steroids, in the extract which has been reported to possess potent anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective effects, as reported by Oliveira *et al.*, (2004).

The study showed that Omega 3 fatty acids (Cod liver oils) which are supplement with *Ocimum sanctum* in this work possess anti-malarial anti-inflammatory, self-defensive agent as reported by Schumann, (2011) and Lutgen, (2016). Omega 3 fatty acids have also shown to block sporozoites invasion and boost the immune system; this inhibition of sporozoite invasion could be related to the production of potent bacteriocidal protein BPI by EPA and DHA. It is also showed that BPI is active against *Leishmania*, *Trypanosoma*, *Plasmodium*, and *Toxoplasma* as reported by Robinson, (2012) and Tiago *et al.*, (2015). Fish oils rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAS) cause a marked in vitro growth inhibition of *plasmodia*. Similar effects were seen in vivo on mice infected with *plasmodium berghei* and treated during 4 days with fatty acids. The effect is not only suppressive but also prophylactic reported by Kumartilake *et al.*, (2015)

CONCLUSION RECOMMENDATION

This study showed that extract of *Ocimum sanctum* and omega 3 fatty acid possesses antimalarial effect confirming the report of earlier workers. The synergistic extract at different concentration has a tendency of restoring liver damage and treating malaria.

Further research is needed to understand the mechanism of action by using vitro model to figure out the effectiveness of synergistic extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* and Omega 3 fatty acids as anti-malarial drugs.

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